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Two Different Textile Antennas Designed for Unipolar Feed and Deployment in Clothing Apparatus

S. A. Mitilineos¹, S. Jevsnik², S. Vassiliadis¹, S. M. Potirakis¹, N. A. Stathopoulos¹, S. K. Bahadir³

¹ Piraeus University of Applied Sciences, 250, Thivon str., 122 44, Aigaleo, GREECE

²Inlas d.o.o., Grajska ulica 3, 3210 Slovenske Konjice, SLOVENIA

³Istanbul Technical University, Textile Technologies and Design Faculty, inonu caddesi No:67 34437 Beyoglu-Istanbul, TURKEY

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Abstract

Textile antennas have recently attracted significant research resources due to their potential to be used for communications and medical applications in a seamless manner. The respective research field is very active and ongoing research includes new materials and techniques for robustness, durability and credibility of designs. A series of textile antennas have been designed, fabricated and tested during the ongoing work within the context of the ETexWeld Marie-Curie Research Project. Herein, we present two textile antennas that are designed to operate in close vicinity or in contact with the human body. The first one is a rectangular spiral antenna with unipolar feeding and modified layout and the second one is a planar dipole that is modified to operate with unipolar feed connector. The main goal of the proposed designs was to implement textile antennas that are easily and cost-efficiently implemented using textile technologies like knitting and sewing. Both proposed antennas were implemented by sewing conductive yarns over conventional fabric in a way that the shape of the antenna is developed in an accurate manner. The simulated and measured results of the proposed antennas encourage their implementation using alternative textile technologies like welding and embroidery.

1. Introduction

Textile antennas have recently attracted significant research resources due to their potential to be used for communications and medical applications in a seamless manner [1, 2]. However, RF and high frequency characterization of textile materials is a challenging task. The

electromagnetic properties of antennas are sensitive to their geometry, dimensions and dielectric characteristics of the materials used [3, 4]. Given that regular clothing use also involves bending, crumpling and other unforeseen anomalies on the shape of the antenna, it becomes evident that textile antennas developers need to overcome a demanding amount of limitations and restrictions. The respective research field is very active and ongoing research includes new materials and techniques for robustness, durability and credibility of designs. During the ongoing research that is implemented within the context of the ETextWeld Marie-Curie Research Project a series of textile antennas have been designed, fabricated and tested. Examples of already performed work on development of textile antennas may be found in [5-8]. In this work we present two different textile antenna implementations that are both fed by unipolar transmission lines. The first one is a rectangular spiral antenna that is a variant of the well-known linear or logarithmic spiral antenna but more suitable for development with textile technology. The inherent multi-band or wideband characteristics of a spiral antenna make it ideal for wideband applications but the procedure of developing a spiral layout on clothing with knitting or sewing is considered to be time consuming and costly. The rectangular layout of the proposed antenna makes it ideal for development with textile technology. On the other hand, a planar dipole antenna is presented that is also fed by a unipolar transmission line. Conventional dipoles are fed using bipolar transmission lines but the latter are difficult to implement with textile technology. Therefore, the proposed unipolarly-fed dipole is considered to be more suitable for development with textile technology. In the following, the rectangular spiral antenna is presented in Section 2 while the textile dipole antenna is presented in Section 3. The paper concludes with Section 4.

2. Textile Rectangular Spiral Antenna

Spiral antennas are a well-known genre of antennas that exhibit frequency-independent radiation characteristics. Due to their particular spiral design with extending arms of increasing width they provide efficient matching of incoming signals over a large frequency range and also provide an efficient means of coupling with the environment and, hence, radiation. The fractional bandwidth of a spiral antenna may be as large as 30:1 and has a radiation pattern with a maximum at a direction perpendicular to the plane of the antenna. Due to the efficient coverage of a very large bandwidth, as well as their circular polarization, spiral antennas may be used in sensing applications despite their relatively lower achieved radiation gain. Depending on the antenna's parameters selection, it is possible to design an antenna with extremely large bandwidth and convenient radiation characteristics.

The proposed rectangular spiral antenna has been designed and optimized using the CST Microwave Studio suite. The conventional design of a linear spiral antenna has been modified in order to be fed by a unipolar transmission line but nevertheless there are concerns about the ease of use in everyday applications of the antenna due to the position of the antenna feeding input at

its centre and away of adjacent electronic components. Furthermore, the circular shape of the antenna makes it difficult to implement using hand sewing. For these reasons, it is considered that it is important to investigate an alternative spiral antenna design with rectangular shape and a feeding input position placed at the outer side of the antenna. The rectangular shape of the proposed antenna overcomes the conventional curved layout of similar antennas found in the literature that makes them unsuitable for development with textile technologies. The layout of the simulated model of the proposed rectangular spiral antenna is depicted in Figure 1. The proposed antenna was manufactured in two different prototypes and its input reflection coefficient was measured within the anechoic chamber of the Piraeus University of Applied Sciences using a ZVA24 Vector Network Analyzer by Rohde & Schwarz. The manufactured prototypes of the proposed antenna are depicted in Figure 2 while the respective measured input reflection coefficient is depicted in Figure 3. The input reflection coefficient of the antenna denotes that it exhibits an ultra wideband behaviour with a tuning range starting from 1.6 GHz up to 7.7 GHz; this is an input bandwidth of more than 6 GHz. There can also be observed two different sharp tuning at the frequencies of 4.8 and 5.7 GHz.

Figure 1: Layout of the simulated model of the proposed rectangular spiral antenna in CST Microwave Studio Suite

Figure 2: Manufactured prototypes of the proposed rectangular spiral antenna

Figure 3: Measured input reflection coefficient of the manufactured rectangular spiral antennas

3. Textile Dipole Antenna

Dipole antennas are a ubiquitous class of antennas with very well known radiation characteristics. However, planar dipole antennas are not as easily designed and deployed as their three-dimensional counterparts while at the same time the need for a bipolar feeding transmission line renders this class of antennas not easily applicable for implementation with textile technology. In this work we present a planar textile dipole antenna that we have designed and optimized in a way that it can accept a unipolar feeding transmission line in order to be readily employed in textile electronic circuits.

The CST model of the proposed dipole antenna is illustrated in Figure 4. The CST model of the antenna also includes the SMA connector that is used in order to feed the antenna using a standard cable that is a unipolar transmission line. Furthermore, the manufactured textile dipole antenna and its measured input reflection coefficient are depicted in Figures 5 and 6, respectively. The proposed dipole exhibits a tuning frequency at 3.16 GHz with an input bandwidth from 2.70 up to 3.84 GHz.

Figure 4: Simulated model of the proposed unipolarly-fed textile dipole antenna

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

4. Conclusions

In this paper, two different textile antennas have been presented. The proposed antennas include a rectangular spiral antenna and a dipole antenna. The contribution of this work lies in that the proposed antennas have been designed taking into account the special constraints and needs of the implementation of antennas using textile technology. Keeping in mind that the proposed antennas need to be integrated into clothing we modified their feeding points and their layout in order to make it easier for them to be developed using knitting or sewing techniques. Indeed, after some initial trials to implement classical spiral and dipole antennas, it became feasible for the ETextWeld Project Team to implement its own textile antennas using these two proposed designs. Furthermore, simulation and measurements results of the proposed antennas are also presented herein.

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